

ELECTRONIC SYSTEM OF DIRECTORS OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS IN WORK WITH STUDENTS ON INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

Khaitov Bekzod Shukhratovich

13.00.02- Theory and methods of education and training 1st stage doctoral student,

E-mail: bkhaitov8855@gmail.com. Kokand State Pedagogical Institute.

ANNOTATION. The article analyzes the pedagogical methods and importance of developing communicative competence in the personal qualities of the head of the educational institution in the formation of the qualities of social and psychological initiative, determination, courage, aspiration to innovation and their acceptance and correct application in practice.

KEYWORD: personality, communication, competence, communicative competence, pedagogy, information technology.

INTRODUCTION.

Conflict is frequently alluded to as conflicting views, clashes that are expressed through intergroup or interpersonal connections related to obnoxious enthusiastic experiences.

From a psychological point of view, a situation that features a devastating effect on people is not the conflict itself, but their result. Conflicts cause negative sentiments in the human mind, such as fear, panic, and animosity. If these experiences are solid and last a long time, a protective reaction can develop and be reinforced in a person.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS.

In today's globalized and informative educational environment, the main task of the management staff of the educational institution is to ensure the independent work of teachers and independent professional self-development, to keep abreast of the latest innovations in the field, innovation. The application of unit technologies in professional activities is determined by the issue of continuous improvement of their professional skills. In this process, the development of modern information and communication skills and competencies of teachers, working to improve their information and communication technologies, work with e-learning resources, implementation, research, pedagogical creativity, The development and implementation of adaptive, creatively oriented educational programs, retraining and advanced training play an important role in the modernization of educational content.

Creative-modular educational technologies are being introduced in Russia, the United States, France and South Korea to develop the active accumulation of managerial qualities in the leadership of the world's leading educational institutions for the successful management of the educational institution. Systematic work is carried out on the continuous development of information and communication competencies of the head of the educational institution, the implementation of major projects to improve the managerial performance of the head in a market economy and innovation.

Formation of motivation for continuous improvement of information and communication competence of the head of the educational institution on the basis of the principle of modern education "life-long learning" in world educational and research institutions, regular assessment of information and communication competence of the head, expanding research opportunities, adapting personal growth needs to the needs of the educational institution. In an informed educational environment, special attention is paid to

improving the theoretical knowledge of the head of the educational institution, diagnosing information and communication competencies, developing the competence of management staff in information technology, improving forms of distance learning.

The analysis of the activities of the head of the secondary school in the developed countries of East Asia, in particular in South Korea, shows that in addition to mathematical, communicative, informational, analytical, socio-cultural competence, allowed to determine the focused competence.

In recent years, the regulatory framework for the innovative development of school education, diligence, initiative, development of personal and professional qualities of the leader, rapid adaptation to new conditions and the definition of its prospects has been created in the country. After all, the priority task is to "turn school education in our country into a nationwide movement on the basis of the great idea that" New Uzbekistan begins at the threshold of school. " In this regard, the opportunity to create effective mechanisms for the formation and development of an active and dynamic leader of the educational institution, who clearly achieves his professional goals, is open to each new initiative and optimistic about innovation.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018 No. PF-5538 "On additional measures to improve the management system of public education", April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "O ' Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", No. PP-4963 of January 25, 2021 This research work also to some extent contributes to the implementation of the tasks set out in the resolution "On measures to be taken" and other regulations related to this activity.

The relevance of the research to the priorities of the development of science and technology in the country. This research was carried out in the framework of the priority direction of the development of science and technology of the republic "In the social, legal, economic, cultural, spiritual and educational development of an informed society and a democratic state, the formation of a system of innovative ideas and ways to implement them."

Organizational and didactic model of development of information and communication skills of heads of secondary schools in the process of digitization of education, based on the identification of diagnostic motives for students' self-development activities and educational and didactic opportunities of advanced foreign experience;

The professional knowledge of the head of the secondary school is based on the analysis of information and the priority of subject-subject relations in joint activities, as well as the stages of adequate development. improved on the basis of harmonization;

Scientific and practical significance of research results. The scientific significance of the research results in the in-depth analysis of the content, essence and structure of the concept of "information and communication competence of heads of secondary schools" explained by the improvement of the model.

Practical significance of the research results Improvement of practical mechanisms for the development of information and communication competence of heads of secondary schools in the process of digitization of education, development of differential diagnostic test kits to assess the level of professional competence of heads of secondary schools, authorship for advanced training is explained by the fact that the program was developed and implemented.

Another group of reasons for the occurrence of conflict can include a system of perceptions that arise in human perception in a conflict situation. A.G.Shmelev, a Russian researcher, while studying the factors that cause conflicts in small groups, argues that the conflict situation escalates into a conflict mode with such a system of perceptions. In particular, in the "system of egocentric perceptions" that take place in human perception, the participant in the conflict puts his interests, goals and needs at the center of the whole situation. Such a person analyzes the consequences of the conflict only in terms of the satisfaction of his personal interests. People, things and events around them are perceived as a means to an end. Such an approach to a situation arising from a conflict of interest is the basis for further escalation of the conflict.

The third type of attitude that is formed in a conflict situation is debated as a "system of socio-centric perceptions". Such a system has a polycentric, i.e. multi-centric, appearance, unlike the previous two monocentric (single-centered) systems. In the "socio-centric system", the resolution of the situation is in the interests of all parties to the conflict, and the person takes into account the needs of the majority in resolving the problem situation.

CONCLUSION.

"You-I" information. Usually, any participant in a conflict claims that their interests are being discriminated against and often tends to blame the other party as the cause of the conflict. In many cases, the development of a conflict situation goes from exposing the faults and shortcomings of the other party to mutual insults. The attention of the parties to the conflict is focused on the other person's personality and lifestyle. For example, "If you didn't do that, it wouldn't be the same result," "Did you forget again,"

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